

**JUST
WIND
4 ALL**

THE ROLE OF MUNICIPALITIES IN A JUST ENERGY TRANSITION

GUIDE FOR LOCAL AUTHORITIES

**JUST
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4 ALL**

The main objective of the Horizon Europa 2020 JustWind4All project (2023–2025) is to inspire, inform and activate dialogue between actors in the European wind energy sector on the theme of justice in the energy transition.

In Portugal, there are two project partners: the Faculty of Sciences of the University of Together, we are working towards a fairer and more sustainable energy transition, namely through greater economic and political participation by citizens and local communities.

What is the energy transition?

It is a process of societal transformation that impacts i) our energy sources – replacing fossil fuels with renewable sources - ii) our networks and the way we distribute, store and manage energy, and finally iii) the way we consume and use that energy..

What is energy justice?

Energy justice is the dimension of this transition that ensures that this process takes place in a democratic, participatory, inclusive and transparent manner, with a fair distribution of costs and benefits.

What are the main pillars of energy justice?

Our stakeholders

1. MUNICIPALITIES AS LEADERS OF THE JUST ENERGY TRANSITION

The energy transition is taking shape in a very concrete and impactful way at the local and regional levels, and it is at this scale that municipalities play a key role, not only as agents of these transformations but also as facilitators of energy justice processes. Their inherent proximity to citizens and other local stakeholders, their autonomy and freedom in terms of municipal policies, their knowledge of the territory and their available resources make public administration one of the main guarantors of democracy, citizen participation, territorial sovereignty and sustainability.

The **Municipal Energy Transition** is based on four fundamental areas of action:

- **Increase citizens' economic participation**
- **Increase public participation and consultation**
- **Promote information, education and training**
- **Increase local decentralised production and distribution**

See some key documents here:

- PNEC 20230 - Council of Ministers Resolution No. 53 of 10 July: <https://diariodarepu-blica.pt/dr/detalhe/resolucao-conselho-minis-tros/53-2020-137618093>
- Network for Energy Sovereignty (Catalonia): <https://xse.cat/>
- Think Tank Fundación Renovables: <https://fundacionrenovables.org/documento/como-liderar-desde-los-ayuntamientos-la-transicion-energetica/>
- RED III: <https://www.dgae.gov.pt/comunicacao/des-taques/transposicao-da-diretiva-red-iii-.aspx>
- Directive 2023/2413: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal->

As actors in local government, **municipalities must balance and mediate the different** economic, social, environmental and cultural **interests** of their regions through actions such as:

Accelerating the implementation of renewable energies and decarbonisation

Maintaining the region's landscape, tourism and cultural values

Regenerating the environment

Ensure economic and social justice for its residents

Municipalities can mobilise the following instruments to achieve a fair and sustainable energy transition:

1. Implement and promote a “**one-stop shop for energy transition**”;
2. Encourage/support/create **energy communities**;
3. Stimulate/support/create **local cooperatives**, local producer/consumer associations and establish public-private partnerships;
4. Create a **participatory budget** for the energy transition;
5. Use **fiscal and financial instruments** to stimulate citizen participation in the energy transition.

2. INFORMATION, TRAINING AND PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

Municipalities play an important role in raising social awareness, empowering local entities, and promoting and sharing knowledge. This new mandate for municipal public officials must be built together with society, in a democratic energy model.

Public participation is therefore a premise and cross-cutting element of municipal energy policies.

Areas: renewable energy, energy efficiency, buildings and mobility.

Target audience: citizens and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs).

Promoters: municipal public entities, consortia, energy agencies.

EXAMPLES OF ACTIVITIES AT MUNICIPAL LEVEL

Information

- Technical reports and local energy assessments
- Databases
- Practice database
- Information hub

Dissemination

- Awareness-raising actions
- Engagement campaigns
- Development and sharing of promotional content (e.g. publications, teaching resources)

Training and action

- Education of children and young people
- Technical training
- Mobilisation of entities
- Experimentation and pilot projects

Public participation

- Planning (e.g. participatory budgeting, strategic plans, master plan)
- Shared vision (e.g. citizens' forum, thematic round tables)
- Mediation (e.g. dialogue circles)

Explore more:

- Citizens' energy forum: <https://icaen.gencat.cat/es/participacio/forum-ciutada-per-lenergia/>
- Podcast – Toda Energia (ADENE/ Antena 1): <https://antena1.rtp.pt/podcast/toda-a-energia/>
- Minuto Energia (ADENE/ RTP): <https://www.adene.pt/comunicacao/videos/>
- Renováveis Magazine: <https://www.renovaveismagazine.pt/>

3. RENEWABLE ENERGY COMMUNITIES

POTENTIAL OF MUNICIPAL RENEWABLE ENERGY COMMUNITIES

RCEs are legal entities (such as associations or cooperatives), made up of public and/or private actors (such as citizens, local authorities and SMEs), which enable the local generation,

sharing and management of renewable energy, extending the environmental, economic and social benefits to the community and the territory where they are located.

Municipal-level RECs offer several opportunities:

- **Proximity to citizens and knowledge of local specificities**
Alignment of REC objectives with the energy needs of the territory.
- **Access to financing**
Use of funds such as PRR, Environmental Fund Environmental Fund and European instruments.
- **Extensive and long-lasting partnerships with various local actors**
- **Integration into local policies**
Inclusion of RECs in PAESCs and Municipal Climate Action Plans.

- **Territorial cohesion and local job creation**
- **Technological and social innovation**
- **Contribution to national targets for decentralised renewable energy generation**

DID YOU KNOW...

Most of the so-called “renewable energy communities” that are being implemented in Portugal are formally collective self-consumption projects?

MUNICIPAL SUPPORT FOR RECS:

Installation of photovoltaic solar panels in public spaces, municipal facilities and housing, under a **collective self-consumption (CSC)** scheme.

Mapping of energy poverty in the municipality, facilitating the adherence of vulnerable households to RECs.

Simplification of municipal administrative processes.

Reduction of fees for the installation of renewable energy systems.

Financial support for economically vulnerable citizens and families, covering the cost of their entry into RECs.

Granting economic and financial incentives for microgeneration of renewable energy, promoting individual self-consumption.

Promotion of co-investment and citizen co-ownership of renewable energy projects:

activation of Article 6(e) of Decree-Law No. 30-A/2022.

Granting of municipal land and/or rights to use the roofs of municipal buildings to citizen-led RECs for the installation of renewable infrastructure.

Free **technical and legal assistance** to citizens and local entities wishing to set up RECs or apply for financial support programmes.

Training of local leaders, promoting the autonomous creation of citizen-based RECs.

Promotion of public-community partnerships between various local actors (local authorities, citizens, higher education institutions, communities, associations), with a view to complementing skills.

Promotion of the circular economy: partnerships with local companies and NGOs to encourage the reuse of energy waste.

Stimulating municipal REC networks to share experiences and best practices.

Useful information:

- Self-consumption and Renewable Energy Community – Legislative Guide, ADENE: <https://www.adene.pt/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Manual-Digital-Autoconsumo-e-Comunidade-de-Energia-Renovavel-Guia-Legislativo.pdf>
- Energy Communities, DGEG: <https://www.dgeg.gov.pt/pt/areas-setoriais/energia/energias-renovaveis-e-sustentabilidade/comunidades-de-energia/>
- Practical guide: Development of renewable energy communities by citizens, associations and local authorities – The example of the Renewable Energy Community: https://jf-lumiar.pt/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/Guia_web_spread.pdf
- BundleUp Next White Paper, Ponto Energia: <https://www.pontoenergia.pt/>

Examples of RECs and CSCs promoted by municipalities:

- Porto: <https://asprelamaissustentavel.pt/>
- Batalha: <https://www.cm-batalha.pt/noticias/entidades-publicas-e-privadas-formalizam-escritura-publica-da-acerbatalha>
- Mangualde: <https://www.cmmangualde.pt/comunidades-de-energia-de-mangualde/>

4. RENEWABLE ENERGY COOPERATIVES

Cooperatives are one of the legal structures that can be used for RECs. They have a long tradition in Central and Northern European countries and are growing rapidly in Catalonia.

REScoop brings together 2,500 European energy communities that are guided by **cooperative principles** and aim for **energy democracy**.

These initiatives are based on **citizen ownership** and **democratic control** of renewable energy projects.

Coopérnico is the only renewable energy cooperative in Portugal and has established **partnerships with local councils** to create RECs and ACCs.

Advantages of renewable energy cooperatives:

1. They keep revenue in the community, boosting **employment** and the **local economy**;
2. They promote **social acceptance of renewable energy** by including citizens as co-investors and co-owners of projects;
3. They provide access to renewable energy at a **fair price**;
4. They keep **individual investment affordable** by mobilising a large number of citizen co-investors;
5. Distribute part of the profits to members and allocate the rest to community projects.

Ílhavo:

1. Part of the COMSOLVE project;
2. Photovoltaic system financed by Coopérnico members, with priority given to residents of Ílhavo;
3. A pioneering case of residents investing in renewable energy production in their own municipality;
4. Renewable energy shared between two municipal buildings, under an ACC scheme;
5. Approximately 56% reduction in annual energy consumption;
6. Basis for a local REC.

For more information:

<https://www.coopernico.org/artigo/354>

Figueira da Foz:

1. Part of the “Affordable Energy for All” project;
2. The municipality granted land to Coopérnico for the construction of a photovoltaic power plant;
3. Investors receive renewable electricity;
4. Main objective: reduction in the electricity bills of participants in Figueira;
5. Basis for a local REC, composed of the municipality, citizens, companies, and social economy entities;
6. Medium term: REC will manage all activities.

For more information:

<https://www.coopernico.org/artigo/355>

5. ENERGY SOVEREIGNTY AND DEMOCRACY

Ensuring an adequate level of energy sovereignty and democracy is one of the critical aspects critical to the resilience of territories and guarantees their sustainability and competitiveness. At this level, municipalities can:

Ensure transparency and access to energy data that enable more agile and intelligent management:

- Share municipal energy data with all stakeholders on a regular basis, including progress in reducing emissions and the effectiveness of energy efficiency projects.
- Develop monitoring platforms where citizens, businesses and other stakeholders can track the energy production of municipal infrastructure in real time, promoting greater awareness and transparency about energy consumption.

Ensuring fair and affordable prices

- Policies to combat energy poverty: create support programmes for households in energy-vulnerable situations, through subsidies or reductions in energy bills for those who produce renewable energy locally.
- Regulation of municipal energy tariffs: where possible, municipalities can push for a tariff structure that reflects the benefits of decentralised energy, reducing inequalities in access to energy.

Municipal and/or regional management of the low-voltage distribution network

- Remunicipalisation of low-voltage (LV) electricity distribution networks: taking advantage of the opportunity provided by the expiry of LV concession contracts and the launch of new tenders (scheduled for 2025) to regain direct operation of the networks by municipalities.

DID YOU KNOW...

Decree-Law No. 15/2022 of 14 January “establishes the organisation and operation of the National Electricity System and determines that the distribution of low voltage (LV) electricity is assigned to municipalities or intermunicipal entities by delegation from the former”.

The municipalities hold the concession for low-voltage electricity distribution, assigned to E-Redes (formerly EDP Distribuição) for a period of 20 years, which ends at different times, but most contracts with the company came to an end between 2021 and 2022.

6. FINANCING MECHANISMS

There are several types of collaborative financing for local, collective, and decentralised renewable energy projects that municipalities can adopt or facilitate.

1. Crowdfunding

Municipal councils can act as facilitators or promoters, ensuring transparency and trust in the process.

Loan: citizens lend capital to the project promoter, expecting future repayment with interest.

Reward: investors receive non-monetary benefits (such as discounts on electricity) in exchange for initial financing.

2. Public-private partnerships

Partnerships with renewable energy

cooperatives to co-finance and manage RECs. The local authority can provide infrastructure for the installation of photovoltaic panels and prioritise investment by residents.

Citizen co-investment in private CCAs: granting municipal CCA projects to private developers, on the condition that citizens can co-invest and participate in management.

DID YOU KNOW...

Go Parity is the first sustainable investment platform in Portugal? It has already enabled the financing of almost 400 projects in sustainable energy, water and the blue economy, businesses in transition, the social economy and sustainable land use in several countries.

For more information:
<https://goparity.com/pt-pt>

Partnership with local companies: companies finance the installation of UPAC in their waterproofed spaces. The municipality takes care of the bureaucratic procedures (licensing, ACC management) and ensures the fair distribution of the surplus (prioritising economically vulnerable families/those in energy poverty).

Agra do Amial Renewable Energy Community (Asprela + Sustentável Project)

Funded by Águas e Energia do Porto (which acts as EGAC) and with technical coordination by AdEPorto, this municipal ACC initiative – a pioneer in Portugal – encompasses 181 homes (mostly municipally managed) and a primary school.

For more information:

<https://asprelamaissustentavel.pt/>

3. Local green bonds and funds:

Municipal green bonds: issued by the municipality to finance local renewable energy projects, namely REC and ACC.

Local energy transition funds: created by local authorities, these can be financed by their own revenues, environmental taxes or European funds. They can support RECs through grants, low-interest loans or financial guarantees.

4. Participatory budgets for energy transition

Allocate a portion of the participatory budget to community-led energy transition projects.

7. TAX INCENTIVES AND LEGAL INSTRUMENTS FOR ENERGY JUSTICE

1. Municipal tax incentives

Reduction of Municipal Property Tax (IMI)

for individual self-consumers, members of ACC projects and participants in RECs.

The case of the Municipality of Porto

The Municipality of Porto already grants [tax benefits](#) for decentralised renewable energy production by reducing the IMI for owners of urban buildings located in the municipality who have installed renewable production units for individual self-consumption, but also for owners who participate in ACC or REC.

See the [Municipal Portal](#) for more information.

Reduction of IMI and possibility of exemption from urban taxes for companies participating in municipal ACC projects, in return for financing the UPAC or the provision of their roofs or waterproofed spaces.

2. Citizen co-investment in renewable energy projects

Require private developers to open projects to local populations, establishing a minimum threshold for citizens' economic participation (individually or through renewable energy communities and cooperatives).

International inspiration: the case of Denmark

Since 2009, the Renewable Energy Act has required all wind energy developers to offer a 20% share to residents living near new wind farms.

3. Integration of decentralised renewable generation into urban planning

Energy zoning: identifying priority areas for the collective decentralisation of renewable energy.

Urban planning requirements: requiring private developers to install renewable infrastructure (such as photovoltaic panels and batteries) in new buildings and, where possible, in renovations.

DID YOU KNOW...

According to Article 6(e) of Decree-Law No. 30-A/2022, the involvement of local communities in the installation of renewable energy power plants may include measures aimed at granting the local population the option of co-investing in the power plant?

Other sources of information and training on energy transition:

The Green Deal and Energy Transition in Portugal European

Union Mayors' Climate and Energy Pact

RESCOOP.EU

Resources and tools from the European Federation of Energy Communities

ADENE Academy Training Portfolio

ERSE educational and informational materials

Portugal Energy

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